

PATULIN AND ITS IMPORTANCE FOR HEALTH: A REVIEW

Hasan Pinar^{1*}

ABSTRACT

Keywords

Foods,
Mycotoxin,
Patulin,
Health.

Patulin is produced as a secondary metabolite by *Aspergillus*, *Byssoschlamys*, and *Penicillium* species. The maximum patulin value recommended by the World Health Organization is $50 \mu\text{g L}^{-1}$. *Penicillium expansum* is considered the sole fungal species responsible for patulin contamination in stone fruits, particularly in apples and apple-based products. Patulin, the most commonly encountered mycotoxin type, is an important carcinogen for public health. The formation of patulin in foods, especially in fruits and vegetables, is a significant concern for the global food industry. Therefore, effective detection of patulin and adoption of reduction strategies are important. Careful consideration of patulin's structure, properties, effects on health, and its removal from foods can contribute to reducing toxic effects such as immunosuppressive, neurotoxic, nephrotoxic, cytotoxic, clastogenic, hepatotoxic, mutagenic, genotoxic, carcinogenic, and teratogenic effects that may occur on human health. Additionally, it provides information about detecting and controlling its harmful consequences. This review has been undertaken to examine the characteristics of patulin, a mycotoxin type, its effects on human health, and to provide guidance on its harmful effects.

INTRODUCTION

Mycotoxins are natural toxins with low molecular weight and diverse chemical structures that occur in fungal species such as *Aspergillus*, *Penicillium*, *Fusarium*, *Alternaria*, and *Claviceps*^{1,2}. More than 400 different mycotoxin types with different toxicity levels have been identified³. They are toxic metabolites produced by certain mold fungi under specific humidity and temperature conditions that can cause unwanted physiological and pathological changes in humans and animals^{4,6}. Moreover, mycotoxins are secondary metabolites produced by fungi that can contaminate various food substances, including foods obtained from fruits and fruit products^{2,7,8}. Today, there are many mycotoxin types produced by mold fungi. However, not every mold fungus possesses toxic properties, just as not every secondary metabolite may exhibit toxic effects⁵.

Exposure to mycotoxins can occur directly through consumption of contaminated foods or indirectly through by-products of animals that consume contaminated feed³. The most important characteristic of mycotoxins is their "carry over" property. As a result of animals consuming toxin-containing feeds, toxins can pass through when humans consume foods obtained from animals such as meat, eggs, and milk^{1,9}. These toxins have serious toxic effects on human health⁴. Among the mycotoxins that are the most common source of concern for humans and farm animals are aflatoxins, citrinin, ochratoxins, fumonisins, zearalenone, nivalenol, deoxynivalenol, fumonisins, and ergot alkaloids. Patulin is also one of the most frequently encountered mycotoxins in fruits and fruit products^{1,7}.

Patulin can emerge during food processing or storage and can also lead to the formation of other toxic compounds. It can also interact with other components in foods, which affects its bioavailability and toxicity. Therefore, even though patulin is not considered a masked mycotoxin, it is important to monitor and control its presence in food products. The masking of mycotoxins in food products can make their detection difficult⁷. In a study conducted, masked patulin was detected in apple juice, apple puree, and apple vinegar samples using high-performance liquid chromatography (HPLC) and fluorescence detection¹⁰.

Volume: 4

Issue: 1

Page: 31–39

Received: 25.11.2025

Accepted: 12.01.2026

Available online: 28.02.2026

DOI:10.5281/zenodo.18935343

The clinical picture that develops due to mycotoxin intake is called "mycotoxicosis"⁵. However, this picture is quite difficult to define and is characterized by one or more diseases. The severity and occurrence of symptoms seen in mycotoxicosis are affected by the type of disease, the type and amount of mycotoxin exposed to, the presence of multiple mycotoxins, personal characteristics such as body weight, physical and nutritional status, environmental conditions, and moisture content⁴.

Patulin, an important mycotoxin type, is receiving global attention and constitutes a source of concern for the entire world because it creates mutagenic, carcinogenic, neurotoxic, genotoxic, immunotoxic, and gastrointestinal effects on human and animal health and further increases disease formation risks⁷. Moreover, patulin, which constitutes a serious public health problem, should not be overlooked due to its potential risks and widespread presence in foods, and its formation should be prevented. Since patulin is a toxic compound, it is important to investigate its adverse or toxic effects on humans and animals. Understanding patulin formation, accumulation,

and affecting factors can help reduce the risk of mycotoxin contamination. Therefore, this review study has been undertaken to examine the characteristics of patulin, a mycotoxin type, its effects on human health, and to provide guidance on its harmful effects.

Patulin structure

Patulin is a toxic mycotoxin produced by mold fungi such as *Penicillium*, *Aspergillus*, and *Byssoschlamys*, particularly *Penicillium expansum* and *Penicillium patulum*^{1,2,5,11,12}. Patulin has a 4-hydroxy-4H-furo[3,2-c]pyran-2(6H)-one structure (Figure 1)^{11,12}. It is colorless, crystalline, and soluble in water and various solvents such as ethanol, methanol, acetone, and ethyl acetate¹³⁻¹⁶. Patulin is a highly reactive unsaturated gamma lactone with a general formula of $C_7H_6O_4$ and a molecular weight of $154.12 \text{ g mol}^{-1}$ ^{11,17-19}. Due to its good solubility in water and chemical stability, it can easily contaminate the environment, foods, and the human body¹⁹. They are toxic chemical compounds with low molecular weight and low volatility².

Figure 1. The Chemical Structure of Patulin

The melting point of patulin is $110-112^\circ\text{C}$ ^{12,13,20}. Patulin exhibits ultraviolet absorbance properties at 276 nm. It is stable in acid and resistant to heat, making it difficult to remove during food processing^{7,18,21}. Therefore, it can remain unchanged in acidic environments, but may undergo chemical changes and lose its activity in alkaline environments²². Due to containing a lactone ring in its structure, it is extremely sensitive to alkalis and easily loses its biological activity. Patulin is an electrophilic molecule that shows its harmful effects by covalently binding to cellular sulfhydryl groups of proteins and glutathione¹⁵. Therefore, it interacts irreversibly with nucleophilic groups²³. It has high polarity and low molecular mass, generally leading to low recoveries and/or low sensitivity²⁴.

Patulin is isolated by some species of *Penicillium*, *Byssoschlamys*, and *Aspergillus*^{7,12}. Both *Penicillium* and *Aspergillus* have the ability to grow at low temperatures. On the other hand, fungi of the *Byssoschlamys* genus are responsible for patulin production in post-pasteurization stages²⁰. Patulin, is a digestive waste product of mold fungi found in fruits, processed products, and other foods¹⁷. Patulin is produced by more than 60 fungal species belonging to more than 30 genera^{25,26}.

Penicillium expansum, which produces patulin, has psychrophilic characteristics²⁵. This mold develops quite well at 0°C and can also develop at -2 to -3°C . The optimum development temperature is 25°C , while the maximum

development temperature is 35°C. The minimum water activity value for patulin production is 0.95, and the optimum pH range for patulin synthesis in foods is 3-6.5. The half-life of patulin has been determined as 64 hours at pH 8 and 1310 hours at pH 6²⁷.

How did patulin emerge?

Patulin first emerged in the 1940s after Fleming's discovery of Penicillin, as toxic lactones produced particularly by *Penicillium expansum* and *Penicillium patulum*, and used as antibiotics^{13,26,28,29}. Patulin, discovered as an antibiotic, received names such as claviformin, penicidin, clavatin, clavacin, expansine, gigantic acid, and myocin C²⁹. Initially, patulin was discovered as a broad-spectrum antifungal antibiotic, and it was determined to inhibit more than 75 different species, including both Gram-positive and Gram-negative bacteria^{14,22,25,29}. Subsequently, in the 1960s, until it was proven to be toxic and classified as a mycotoxin, it was used as an antibiotic and antifungal agent both as a throat and nasal spray to treat colds and as an ointment for fungal skin infections^{2,7,11,29}. Although it possessed antimicrobial properties, it was found to be toxic to a wide variety of other biological systems, including rats, cats, rabbits, and mice¹⁴. Therefore, its use as an antibiotic was abandoned due to its toxicity to many systems²⁶. However, from the 1950s to the 1960s, it was determined to be toxic not only to fungi and bacteria but also to mammalian cell cultures, plants (wheat, corn, lettuce, peas, flax, etc.), and animals, and was reclassified as a mycotoxin^{6,20,25,29}.

Occurrence of patulin in foods

Mycotoxins are toxicologically important because they cause serious diseases and death in animals and humans through the ingestion of contaminated food products². Patulin poses a serious threat because it can start from a single post-harvest fruit and cause contamination of all fruits and spoilage of all stored fruits^{7,30}. *Penicillium expansum*, the most serious post-harvest pathogen of apples, can penetrate the fruit peel through existing injuries while in the field and continue to grow and produce patulin during storage³¹.

Patulin is stable in acid and has heat-resistant properties. Although patulin is not stable in wet grains, it is stable in dry grains and during apple wine production². It is commonly found in products such as apples, apple juice, apple juice concentrate, apple jam, and confectionery⁸. However, it has

also been detected in high-acid fruits and vegetables such as pears, apricots, peaches, tomatoes, grapes, cherries, strawberries, cornelian cherry, black currants, kiwi, oranges, pineapples, and their products, in moldy fruits, grains, and legumes^{2,5-7}. The use of overripe fruits is the main factor of fungal contamination and appears as brown rot in apples, peaches, bananas, apricots, and pineapples¹². Since fruits contain large amounts of water and sugar, this situation increases patulin activity⁷. Destructive decay caused by *Penicillium expansum* typically manifests with characteristic symptoms that are circular and concentric, pale brown, dry, smooth spots. These lesions rapidly spread to the fruit surface and also to the depths of the fruit tissue. The surface of the layer rots may be covered with white spots that develop to form bluish-green fruit structures³¹ (Figure 2). *Penicillium expansum*, which is the source of "blue mold deterioration", a destructive fruit disease more commonly seen in apples and apple products, is abundantly found in stone fruits and pome fruits^{8,12,14}. *Penicillium expansum* is the most widespread in soil and air, adapting well to environmental conditions¹². Although the optimum temperature for *Penicillium expansum* growth is 25°C, it can survive at -3°C. Patulin production decreases as the temperature drops to freezing temperature (0-4°C), and the moisture content should be in the range of 0.82-0.83 for spore formation. Additionally, *Penicillium expansum* can grow in low O₂ atmospheric concentrations and can be found at levels as low as 2%. Furthermore, the level of mold growth and consequent patulin production varies depending on the type of fruit, toxigenic properties of the mold causing contamination, environmental factors such as water activity, temperature, pH and acid content, storage properties, genetic structure of the plant, physical and chemical properties of fruits, such as hardness, peel thickness, sugar content, pH, and presence of antimicrobial compounds^{6,7,12}.

Patulin incidence

The highest acceptable patulin value determined by the Turkish Food Codex in Turkey is 0.05 mg kg⁻¹ (Table 1)³². The maximum patulin value recommended by the World Health Organization is 50 µg L⁻¹^{18,19,23,25}.

For children, the patulin limit in apple juice is recommended at the level of 25 µg kg⁻¹ and even below (10 µg kg⁻¹)^{2,22}. The European Union has set the maximum patulin limit in baby food products at 10 µg kg⁻¹¹⁹. For solid apple products intended for direct consumption by adults, it is 25 µg kg⁻¹^{1,33}.

Countries such as China, the United States, and Canada have determined the maximum patulin level in foods, particularly in apple products, to be in the range of 25 to 50 $\mu\text{g kg}^{-1}$ ³⁰. The United States Food and Drug Administration (FDA) and the European Union have set the maximum limit for patulin in apple juice, apple wine, and apple juice concentrate at 50 $\mu\text{g kg}^{-1}$ ^{7,12}. In countries outside the European Union, particularly in Australia, Iran, and Turkey, it is reported that patulin levels are at levels exceeding European Union limits (30-40% more)^{34,35}. Additionally, it is also reported that the situation regarding patulin contamination of foods in other countries, such as Japan, Pakistan, China, Cameroon, and the Czech Republic, is not appropriate³⁶.

In a study conducted between 2016-2018, it was determined that patulin levels in apple juice and apple-based baby foods were below the European Union limit in most samples, but exceeded the limit in some countries such as Poland and

Italy³⁷. In a study conducted between 2015-2016, it was found that most of the tested apple juice samples (95%) were below the FDA guidance level, but some imported apple juice samples had higher levels³⁸.

Figure 2. Decay in the Apple

Table 1: Highest limits reported for patulin in foods according to the Turkish Food Codex³²

Food Item	Maximum Limit ($\mu\text{g kg}^{-1}$)	
Fruit juices, fruit juice produced from concentrate, concentrated fruit juice, and fruit nectars.	50	The maximum limit for concentrated fruit juice applies to fruit juice produced from concentrate.
Distilled alcoholic beverages obtained from apples or containing apple juice, apple wine, and other fermented beverages.	50	
Solid apple products (including apple compote and apple puree for direct consumption).	25	Apple compote and apple puree are included.
Apple juice and solid apple products: Those labeled and marketed for babies and young children.	10	The maximum limit, including apple compote and apple puree, applies to ready-to-consume products (prepared according to the instructions for use declared by the manufacturer or marketed as ready for direct consumption).
Non-cereal-based complementary foods.	10	The maximum limit applies to ready-to-consume products (prepared according to the instructions for use declared by the manufacturer or marketed as ready for direct consumption).

Studies conducted on patulin

While most studies conducted on patulin are related to apple juices, there are also studies conducted on other fruits and fruit juices. It has been determined that patulin levels in apple and apple-based in Pakistan are found in 58.9% samples of apple and apple-based products, with a mean of 49.8 $\mu\text{g/kg}$ (maximum 396 $\mu\text{g/kg}$) contained³⁹. In another study²³ conducted with apple juices in Iran, patulin levels were found to be negative in 31 samples (48%) and positive in 33 samples

(52%) in the range of 5.102-26.484 $\mu\text{g kg}^{-1}$. In a study conducted in Pakistan, the frequency of patulin occurrence in mango samples was determined as 61.7%, and it was observed that rotted mango fruits were the fruits most contaminated with patulin. In the same study, the toxin occurrence rate in orange samples was determined as 52.5%, showing that patulin is a problem in fruits, fruit juices, and especially in solid products obtained from mango³⁰. Another study conducted on various fruits, fruit juices, and smoothies in Pakistan showed that

patulin was found in 57.4% of the samples (at levels ranging from 0.04 to 1100 $\mu\text{g kg}^{-1}$)⁴⁰. Patulin was analyzed by High-Performance Liquid Chromatography (HPLC) in 20 peach puree, 10 cherry puree, 22 apricot puree, and 14 apricot juice concentrate samples produced in Turkey, and no patulin was found in any of the cherry puree samples. Patulin was found in only 8 of the 20 peach puree samples (3.3 $\mu\text{g kg}^{-1}$ - 17.5 $\mu\text{g kg}^{-1}$). While patulin was found in all 14 apricot juice concentrate samples (11.2 $\mu\text{g kg}^{-1}$ - 17.8 $\mu\text{g kg}^{-1}$), patulin was found in only 7 of the apricot puree samples (13.7 $\mu\text{g kg}^{-1}$ - 23.0 $\mu\text{g kg}^{-1}$)⁴¹. In another study conducted with dried figs in Turkey, high patulin levels (39.3-151.6 $\mu\text{g kg}^{-1}$) were detected⁴². In a study conducted with apples and pears in Argentina by Funes and Resnik (2009)⁴³, the patulin level was 17-221 $\mu\text{g kg}^{-1}$, in Murillo-Arbizu and et al. (2009)⁴⁴ study with apple juice in Spain it was 0.7-118.7 $\mu\text{g kg}^{-1}$, in Forouzan and Madadlou's (2014)⁴⁵ study with apple juice in Azerbaijan it was determined as 29.58-151.2 $\mu\text{g kg}^{-1}$. Rahimi and Jeiran's (2015)⁴⁶ study with various fruit juices (apple, pineapple, pear, peach, pomegranate, and white and red grape juices, etc.) in Iran patulin level was 5-190.7 $\mu\text{g kg}^{-1}$, and in Dural's (2020)² study with baby food in Turkey it was determined as 7.24-38.24 $\mu\text{g kg}^{-1}$. A study conducted in Turkey showed that patulin levels in apple juice and apple-based products are generally low, but higher levels were found in some samples⁴⁷.

Health effects of patulin

Fruits are fundamental food sources for humans and are an essential part of human nutrition. However, mycotoxin contamination is a threat to consumer health and safety. Consumption of foods contaminated with patulin can cause acute, chronic, and cellular-level health problems in humans⁷. It has been reported that the toxic effect of patulin in humans is not fully elucidated; its carcinogenic properties are questionable^{5,7}, but it damages the immune system of animals¹, and it is a carcinogenic substance that is toxic to plants and animals due to its unsaturated lactone structure⁴⁸. Patulin has a precursor known as 6-methylsalicylic acid; together, they are acetyl-CoA derivatives, which makes them polyketides and potential carcinogens¹.

Patulin has been classified as a group three human carcinogen by the International Agency for Research on Cancer¹⁴. It is reported that patulin causes dermatotoxicity, hepatotoxicity,

neurotoxicity, nephrotoxicity, and mutagenic effects in animals³⁶. However, it is also stated that humans exposed to patulin through consumption of infected products may experience toxic effects such as immunosuppressive, neurotoxic, nephrotoxic, cytotoxic, clastogenic, hepatotoxic, mutagenic, genotoxic, carcinogenic, and teratogenic effects, resulting in severe toxicosis^{2,24,28,49,50}. Patulin has the ability to cause gene mutations in different mammalian cells¹¹. It has also been shown that patulin arrests the G1/S cell cycle in human colon cancer cells and induces cell apoptosis in human leukemia cells and colorectal cancer cells⁵.

Patulin is particularly an important carcinogen for public health^{11,27}. Since the molecular structures of mycotoxins are very diverse, they have the ability to cause major changes in the human genome that can lead to cancer development^{9,11}.

Poisoning caused by mycotoxins in humans and animals is called "mycotoxicosis," and different toxic symptoms can be observed depending on the type of mycotoxin, the dose, and the time of exposure⁵. In cases of using inappropriate food processing and storage methods, experiencing malnutrition problems, and lacking protective legal regulations, people can be exposed to mycotoxins by consuming plant-based foods contaminated with toxins or by consuming animal products containing mycotoxins or their metabolites⁹. Additionally, humans can also be indirectly exposed by consuming animals fed with infected feed¹. Although human contact is usually through contaminated foods, it can also occur through skin contact and the respiratory tract, albeit less frequently⁴. Mycotoxicoses are classified as acute or chronic, like all toxigenic syndromes. In acute toxicity, rapid onset and clear toxic response are usually observed, while in chronic toxicity, long-term low-dose exposure occurs, resulting in effects such as cancer or immunodeficiency⁹.

It is stated that patulin alters intestinal barrier function. When contaminated food is consumed, the intestine is the first organ to contact mycotoxins, and intestinal epithelial cells become the target of these toxins²⁶. When patulin is taken in high doses, it suppresses the immune system and causes significant damage, especially in the digestive system. It is reported that when patulin is taken orally, it causes conditions such as gastrointestinal hyperemia, edema and ulceration, bloating, nausea, vomiting, hemorrhage, hypertension, elevated blood sugar, infection in connective tissue, spleen damage, and

kidney obstruction^{1,11,23}. It can also lead to problems such as intestinal injuries. Patulin causes inactivation of the active site of protein tyrosine phosphatase (PTP). This protein is a key regulator of intestinal epithelial barrier function, and the active site of PTP contains a cysteine residue (Cys215)¹. Compounds that react with sulfhydryl, such as acetaldehyde, reduce transepithelial resistance through covalent modification of the cysteine residue Cys215 of PTP. This toxicity can lead to damage in intestinal cells, causing intestinal and gastric cancer. It induces the formation of micronuclei containing all chromosomes and also induces the formation of micronuclei containing acentric chromosomal fragments, which demonstrates its clastogenic ability^{1,11}.

Acute effects resulting in death can also be observed in living beings, depending on the doses taken and individual resistance. Acute and chronic exposure to patulin can also cause damage to the respiratory and urinary systems, paralysis of the nervous system, and health problems such as agitation, convulsions, dyspnea, and pulmonary congestion^{7,28,29}. In the first year of life, especially infants and children, may be more exposed to toxins compared to adults due to low body weight, higher metabolite rates, lower detoxification abilities, and incomplete development of some organs and tissues⁴⁸. Therefore, the detection of patulin in food substances poses a serious problem.

It has been reported that patulin disrupts Deoxyribose Nucleic Acid (DNA) synthesis¹². Associated health problems such as DNA damage, kidney damage, DNA/Ribonucleic acid mutations, growth disorders in children, gene modifications, and immune disorders are reported¹. Patulin has an electrophilic structure due to the conjugated double bonds in its structure. Due to this property, it interacts irreversibly with nucleophilic groups. The presence of patulin also causes structural toxicity by permanently altering the structure of various proteins, including glutathione and DNA^{23,35}.

Patulin is suggested that it can lead to cytotoxicity and genotoxicity by permanently altering the structure of various proteins, including glutathione, which contains cysteine protein and plays an important role in protecting the cell against damage, and DNA. Patulin is considered to be clastogenic in mammalian cells. It is particularly reported to have mutagenic effects in cells with low glutathione levels, leading to increases in chromosomal aberrations and increased micronucleus formation⁵.

Most of the information about patulin toxicity has been obtained from animal studies, and it is reported that there is very little experimental data on acute or chronic toxicity in humans²⁹. It has been reported to cause immunotoxic, genotoxic, neurotoxic, embryotoxic, and gastrointestinal effects in rodents^{2,13,21}. It has been confirmed that patulin is toxic to mice born to mothers treated with patulin, and deaths have been reported to occur in both males and females. It has been stated that subcutaneous administration of patulin twice a week for 15 months showed the carcinogenic effect of patulin by pointing to the development of malignant tumor cells at the application site¹¹.

Removal of patulin from foods

Effective technologies are needed to reduce or eliminate contamination in foods, prevent patulin proliferation, and remove or decompose patulin. For this purpose, physical, chemical, and biological methods are widely used^{3,33,51}. Preventive measures aimed at preventing mycotoxin formation in fruits and processed products are the most effective approach⁵¹. However, there is no single method to remove or detoxify patulin, and it is stated that a combination of various methods may be a better choice³³. Chemical methods are expensive and may require complex characteristics to carry out the detox process¹⁰. Therefore, both physical and chemical methods are not considered sufficiently effective in removing mycotoxins from food and feed³.

Due to the costly and inadequate nature of the methods used, lower-cost methods such as discarding damaged fruits, frequent washing, and cutting the rotting part before patulin formation begins may be preferred^{25,35}. However, it is difficult to completely destroy patulin or remove it from foods⁹. To solve the patulin problem, it is important that fruits used for fruit juice have a short storage period, are transported to the factory in a short time, and are kept under appropriate conditions and washed appropriately⁴⁸. Collecting fruits under dry conditions during harvest, storing them in clean warehouses, transporting them directly to warehouses, and storing them in cold storage at 1.5–4.0°C within 18 hours after harvest to reduce mold infection can be beneficial. The use of fungicides, pesticides, and other biological control agents in post-harvest cold storage, ensuring storage room hygiene, and controlling atmospheric conditions also play an important role¹².

Physical methods

Heat treatments such as pasteurization and distillation are common preservation methods in food processing²⁵.

Pasteurization is a mild heat treatment used to destroy harmful microorganisms, extend shelf life, and increase food safety. Evaporation and distillation are processes that use heat to remove water and/or volatile components from liquid foods^{25,33}. In a study conducted, patulin content in apples varied between 255 to 653 $\mu\text{g kg}^{-1}$ in the grinding process, 131–406 $\mu\text{g L}^{-1}$ after pasteurization, 91–244 $\mu\text{g L}^{-1}$ after enzymatic treatment, 76–314 $\mu\text{g L}^{-1}$ after microfiltration, and 56–231 $\mu\text{g L}^{-1}$ after evaporation⁵². Since patulin is quite resistant to pasteurization temperatures (e.g., 10 seconds at 90°C), this process alone is not an effective application for reducing patulin levels in fruit juices containing high levels of patulin before pasteurization²⁵. Since patulin is heat-resistant in low pH environments, it cannot be destroyed by pasteurization⁴⁸. Processing stages such as pasteurization, enzymatic treatment, microfiltration, centrifugation, and evaporation are good methods to prevent or control patulin content; however, they cannot be completely decomposed or removed, and may even cause secondary contamination by molds and their toxins during processing due to inappropriate treatment³³.

Additionally, physical methods include ultraviolet radiation, pulsed light use, and high hydrostatic pressure applications. Ultraviolet radiation is commonly used for destroying microorganisms and is also a way to decompose patulin. Pulsed light is a non-thermal food preservation technique involving the use of short (1 μs –0.1 s) broad-spectrum light bursts with wavelengths between 200 and 1100 nm²⁵.

Pressurized water is widely used in removing moldy parts of apples during apple juice production⁶. Washing generally involves immersion in a water bath or application of high-pressure water flow. The primary purpose of the washing step is to remove residues, including dirt, plant material, insects, and molds/fungi. Patulin is a water-soluble molecule, and by adding a washing step, some of the patulin content in the product can be dissolved and removed. The effectiveness of washing can vary between 10% and 100%²⁵.

The use of activated carbon as an adsorbent for the purpose of removing patulin from fruit juice is one of the most common applications. Different types of activated carbon have shown

different effects on patulin removal. Steam-activated carbon is stated to be more effective than chemically activated carbon²⁵.

Chemical methods

Chemical methods have great potential for detoxifying mycotoxins, including patulin, and are probably the most suitable for commercial application in the food industry today³³. Ascorbic acid used in reducing patulin amounts is generally considered safe, relatively inexpensive, and accepted by consumers as a beneficial nutrient (vitamin C). In studies, the degradation of patulin with and without added ascorbic acid was examined between 25 and 85°C, and it was determined that patulin stability decreased in the presence of ascorbic acid^{33,49}. Another study showed that at acidic pH, the presence of ascorbic acid reduces patulin stability, with patulin decreasing to 30% of its initial concentration after 34 days in the presence of ascorbic acid, while this rate was 68–71% in samples without ascorbic acid⁵³. The addition of sulfite, sulfur dioxide, cysteine, and glutathione has been shown to reduce patulin levels during processing and storage⁴⁹.

Chemical processes such as ammoniation, ozonation, and peroxidation have been reported to destroy mycotoxins from food substances³. Among chemical additives, ozone is widely used to detoxify patulin in foods due to its high safety, low cost, environmentally friendly structure that leaves no toxic residues, and ease of use³³. Ozone is a strong oxidant that can react with numerous chemical groups and is stated to be able to detoxify patulin²⁵. Ozone is a strong oxidant and powerful disinfectant substance widely applied in the processing of water, fruits, and vegetables for sterilization purposes and extending shelf life in two forms (gaseous ozone and ozonated water). In a study conducted, ozone treatment significantly affected the amount of patulin in apple juice, reducing it from 201.06 to below 50 $\mu\text{g L}^{-1}$ within 15 minutes with a 75.36% reduction. In the same study, it was determined that the main phenolic compounds and organic acids in apple juice were seriously degraded when subjected to ozone treatment compared to the control group¹⁸. It is stated that ozone alone can decompose patulin by up to 98% in one minute, is quite effective, and does not have a significant effect on the quality parameters of food products²⁵.

As a result of pre-harvest ammonium molybdate application to apple trees, it has been reported that there was a significant

reduction in "blue mold" formation caused by patulin after three months in apples stored in cold storage.

It has been stated that the compound Trans-2-hexenal, an aromatic substance, is a good inhibitor against *Penicillium expansum*. In addition, it has been reported that cleaning crates used for transporting fruits with chlorine compounds (sodium o-phenylphenate and quaternary ammonium) may be beneficial³⁵.

Biological methods

Biological methods refer to all methods that use active or inactive microorganisms or enzymes to reduce patulin in foods²⁵. Depending on the patulin reduction method, biological methods are divided into two types: adsorption and degradation. Active or inactive bacteria are generally used to reduce patulin content in foods through adsorption³³. Detoxification refers to processes that inactivate mycotoxins by chemically altering them or reducing toxicity, while adsorption refers to the means by which mycotoxins are bound and removed from solution²⁵. Biological methods used in the removal and decomposition of mycotoxins are seen as attractive and environmentally friendly³.

CONCLUSION

Patulin is one of the most dangerous toxic substances found in foods and animals, threatening health both in Türkiye and worldwide, with immunosuppressive, neurotoxic, nephrotoxic, cytotoxic, clastogenic, hepatotoxic, mutagenic, genotoxic, carcinogenic, and teratogenic effects. Despite efforts to reduce patulin levels worldwide, they can still be at high levels. To minimize the consumption of patulin through foods, preventing its formation and/or removing patulin from every type of food in which it can form is important for human health, especially for infant health. Therefore, it is recommended not to exceed the recommended limits for patulin and ensure necessary controls, implement healthy agricultural practices, use appropriate food processing and storage methods during the harvest of food products, ensure that people are conscious in consuming existing foods, address the issue seriously, and increase health literacy. Additionally, the moisture content of foods should be limited to certain critical levels, and consumers should follow safe food processing practices, including controlling deterioration in foods and discarding fruits or fruit juices showing signs of deterioration or mold formation.

Conflicts of Interest Statement

There are no potential conflicts of interest.

Acknowledgements

No

REFERENCES

- Awuchi CG, Ondari EN, Nwozo S, Odongo GA, Eseoghene IJ, Twinomuhwezi H, et al. Mycotoxins' toxicological mechanisms involving humans, livestock and their associated health concerns: a review. *Toxins*. 2022; 14: 167.
- Dural E. Monitorization of patulin and hydroxymethylfurfural in fruit juices and commercial fruity baby foods by an HPLC-DAD method. *Revue Roumaine de Chimie*. 2020; 65(2): 191–200.
- Nahle S, El Khoury A, Savvaidis I, Chokr A, Louka N, Atoui A. Detoxification approaches of mycotoxins: by microorganisms, biofilms and enzymes. *International Journal of Food Contamination*. 2022; 9: 3.
- Aghaee EM, Khaniki GJ, Gharagheshlagi HE, Raziabad RH, Karami M. Major mycotoxins in food; hazards, formation and prevention methods. *Current Medical Mycology*. 2018; 4: 46–189.
- Becit M, Aydın S, Baydar T. Genotoxic effects of mycotoxins: review. *Türkiye Klinikleri Journal of Literature Pharmacy Sciences*. 2017; 6(2): 59–76.
- Erdoğan A, Ghimire D, Gürses M, Çetin B, Baran A. Patulin contamination in fruit juices and its control measures. *European Journal of Science and Technology*. 2018; 14: 39–48.
- Bacha SAS, Li Y, Nie J, Xu G, Han L, Farooq S. Comprehensive review on patulin and *Alternaria* toxins in fruit and derived products. *Frontiers in Plant Science*. 2023; 14: 1139757.
- Saleh I, Goktepe I. The characteristics, occurrence, and toxicological effects of patulin. *Food and Chemical Toxicology*. 2019; 129: 301–311.
- Toptaş Ö, Erköse Genç G. Common mycotoxins: aflatoxins, ochratoxin a, fumonisins, deoxynivalenol, zearalenone. *Journal of Ankara Health Sciences*. 2023; 12(1): 87–98.
- Li Y, Zhang X, Nie J, Bacha SAS, Yan Z, Gao G. Occurrence and co-occurrence of mycotoxins in apple and apple products from China. *Food Control*. 2020; 118: 107354.
- Adam MAA, Tabana YM, Musa KB, Sandai DA. Effects of different mycotoxins on humans, cell genome and their involvement in cancer (Review). *Oncology Reports*. 2017; 37: 1321–1336.
- Mahato DK, Kamle M, Sharma B, Pandhic S, Devid S, Dhawan K, et al. Patulin in food: a mycotoxin concern for human health and its management strategies. *Toxicol*. 2021; 198: 12–23.
- Azizi IG, Rouhi S. Determination of patulin in fruit juices and compute of apple and pear. *Journal of Toxicology: Toxin Reviews*. 2013; 32(3): 39–42.
- Li X, Li H, Li X, Zhang Q. Determination of trace patulin in apple-based food matrices. *Food Chemistry*. 2017; 233: 290–301.
- Liu H, Gao X, Niu L, Li X, Song Z. Rapid determination of picogram levels of patulin in apple juice using a flow injection chemiluminescence procedure. *Journal of the Science of Food and Agriculture*. 2008; 88(15): 2744–2748.
- Nie D, Guo D, Huang Q, Guo W, Wang J, Zhao Z, et al. A novel insight into fluorescent sensor for patulin detection using thiol-terminated liposomes with encapsulated coumarin-6 as signal probe. *Sensors & Actuators: B. Chemical*. 2021; 345: 130366.
- da Silva CR, Simoes CT, Vidal JK, Reghelin MA, de Almeida CAA, Mallmann CA. Development and validation of an extraction method using liquid chromatography-tandem mass spectrometry to determine patulin in apple juice. *Food Chemistry*. 2022; 366: 130654.
- Diao, E., Wang, J., Li, X., Wang X, Song H, Gao D. Effects of ozone processing on patulin, phenolic compounds and organic acids in apple juice. *Journal of Food Science and Technology*. 2019; 56(2): 957–965.

19. Li J, Li S, Li Z, Zhou Y, Jin P, Zhang F, et al. Chromium hydroxide nanoparticles-based fluorescent aptameric sensing for sensitive patulin detection: the significance of nanocrystal and morphology modulation. *Talanta*. 2023; 257: 124296.
20. Pires S, Lopes J, Nunes I, Gaspar E. Patulin analysis: Sample preparation methodologies and chromatographic approaches. *Ecotoxicology*. 2012; 75–90.
21. Dias JV, da Silva RC, Pizzutti IR, dos Santos ID, Dassi M, Cardoso CD. Patulin in apple and apple juice: Method development, validation by liquid chromatography-tandem mass spectrometry and survey in Brazilian South supermarkets. *Journal of Food Composition and Analysis*. 2019; 82: 103242.
22. Guo H, Sun Y, Ma P, Khan IM, Duan N, Wang Z. Sensitive detection of patulin based on DNase I-assisted fluorescent aptasensor by using AuNCs-modified truncated aptamer. *Food Control*. 2022; 131: 108430.
23. Lashkarian EE, Lashgarian HE, Shahzaman, K, Sepahvand A. Measurement of the Patulin toxicant using high performance liquid chromatography (HPLC) in apple juices supplied in Khorramabad City, Iran. *International Journal of Medical Research & Health Sciences*. 2016; 5(11): 229–237.
24. Beltrán E, Ibáñez M, Sancho JV, Hernández F. Determination of patulin in apple and derived products by UHPLC–MS/MS. Study of matrix effects with atmospheric pressure ionisation sources. *Food Chemistry*. 2014; 142: 400–407.
25. Ioi JD, Zhou T, Tsao R, Marcone MF. Mitigation of patulin in fresh and processed foods and beverages. *Toxins*. 2017; 9(5): 157.
26. Puel O, Pierre Galtier Oswald IP. Biosynthesis and toxicological effects of patulin. *Toxins*. 2010; 2: 613–631.
27. Öksüztepe G, Erkan S. Mycotoxins and their importance in terms of public health. *Journal of Harran University Faculty of Veterinary Medicine*. 2016; 5(2): 190–195.
28. Sadok I, Szmagara A, Staniszewska MM. The validated and sensitive HPLC-DAD method for determination of patulin in strawberries. *Food Chemistry*. 2018; 245: 346–370.
29. Sajid M, Mehmood S, Yuan Y, Yue T. Mycotoxin patulin in food matrices: Occurrence and its biological degradation strategies. *Drug Metabolism Reviews*. 2019; 51(1): 105–120.
30. Hussain S, Asi MR, Iqbal M, Khalid N, Wajih-ul-Hassan S, Ariño A. Patulin mycotoxin in mango and orange fruits, juices, pulps, and jams marketed in Pakistan. *Toxins*. 2020; 12: 52.
31. Tannous J, Keller NP, Atoui A, El Khoury A, Lteif R, Oswald IP, et al. Secondary metabolism in *penicillium expansum*: emphasis on recent advances in patulin research. *Critical Reviews in Food Science and Nutrition*. 2018; 58(12): 2082–2098.
32. Turkish Food Codex. Communiqué on the determination of maximum levels of certain contaminants in foodstuffs. 2008 [<https://www.resmigazete.gov.tr/eskiler/2008/05/20080517-7.htm>, Accessed 20 September 2025].
33. Diao E, Hou H, Hu W, Dong H, Li X. Removing and detoxifying methods of patulin: a review. *Trends in Food Science & Technology*. 2018; 81: 139–145.
34. Iha MH, Sabino M. Determination of patulin in apple juice by liquid chromatography. *Journal of AOAC International*. 2006; 89(1): 139–143.
35. Şahin G, Ünüvar S, Baydar T. Patulin: toksisitesi ve bebek beslenmesinde kullanılan ürünlerde olası bulaşma. *Türk Pediatri Arşivi*. 2011; 46(4): 275–279.
36. Lu S., Liu S., Cui J., Liu X, Zhao C, Fan L, et al. Combination of patulin and chlorpyrifos synergistically induces hepatotoxicity via inhibition of catalase activity and generation of reactive oxygen species. *Journal of Agricultural and Food Chemistry*. 2019; 67(41): 11474–11480.
37. Gaugain M, Fourmond MP, Fuselier RG, Verdon E, Roudaut B, Pessel D. Control of antimicrobials in feed using liquid chromatography–tandem mass spectrometry: assessment of cross-contamination rates at the farm level. *Journal of Agricultural and Food Chemistry*. 2020; 68(34): 9033–9042.
38. Biango-Daniels MN, Snyder AB, Worobo RW, Hodge KT. Fruit infected with *paecilomyces niveus*: a source of spoilage inoculum and patulin in apple juice concentrate? *Food Control*. 2019; 97: 81–86.
39. Hussain S, Asi MR, Iqbal M, Akhtar M, Imran M, Ariño A. Surveillance of Patulin in Apple, Grapes, Juices and Value-Added Products for Sale in Pakistan. *Foods*. 2020; 9(12):1744.
40. Iqbal SZ, Malik S, Asi MR, Selamat J, Malik N. Natural occurrence of patulin in different fruits, juices and smoothies and evaluation of dietary intake in Punjab, Pakistan. *Food Control*. 2018; 84: 370–374.
41. Akbulut M. Determination of patulin by high performance liquid chromatography in some fruit juices and concentrates produced in Turkey. *Journal of Selcuk University Faculty of Agriculture*. 2005; 19(35): 84–86.
42. Karaca H, Nas S. Aflatoxins, patulin and ergosterol contents of dried figs in Turkey. *Food Additives & Contaminants*. 2006; 23(5): 502–508.
43. Funes GJ, Resnik SL. Determination of patulin in solid and semisolid apple and pear products marketed in Argentina. *Food Control*. 2009; 20: 277–280.
44. Murillo-Arbizu M, Amezcua S, Gonzalez-Peñas E, de Cerain AL. Occurrence of patulin and its dietary intake through apple juice consumption by the Spanish population. *Food Chemistry*. 2009; 113: 420–423.
45. Forouzan SH, Madadlou A. Incidence of patulin in apple juices produced in West Azerbaijan Province, Iran. *Journal of Agricultural Science and Technology*. 2014; 16: 1613–1622.
46. Rahimi E, Jeiran MR. Patulin and its dietary intake by fruit juice consumption in Iran. *Food Additives & Contaminants: Part B Surveillance*. 2015; 8(1): 40–43.
47. Icli N. Occurrence of patulin and 5-hydroxymethylfurfural in apple sour, which is a traditional product of Kastamonu, Turkey. *Food Additives Contaminants: Part A*. 2019; 36(6): 952–963.
48. Oskay N. Survey of patulin occurrence in fruit juices and detoxification of patulin by lactic acid bacteria. 2012. Master's Thesis.
49. Kokkinidou S, Floros JD, LaBorde LF. Kinetics of the thermal degradation of patulin in the presence of ascorbic acid. *Journal of Food Science*. 2014; 79: 108–114.
50. Sadok I, Stachniuk A, Staniszewska M. Developments in the monitoring of patulin in fruits using liquid chromatography: an overview. *Food Analytical Methods*. 2019; 12: 76–93.
51. Yang J, Li J, Jiang Y, Duan X, Qu H, Yang B, et al. Natural occurrence, analysis, and prevention of mycotoxins in fruits and their processed products. *Critical Reviews in Food Science and Nutrition*. 2014; 54(1): 64–83.
52. Welke JE, Hoeltz M, Dottori HA. Effect of processing stages of apple juice concentrate on patulin levels. *Food Control*. 2009; 20: 48–52.
53. Drusch S, Kopka S, Kaeding J. Stability of patulin in a juice-like aqueous model system in the presence of ascorbic acid. *Food Chemistry*. 2007; 100(1): 192–197.